

Energy and Exergy investigation of a solar-driven heat upgrade unit based on the reverse Brayton cycle

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Solar energy exploitation for covering industrial energy requirements is a crucial technology for achieving sustainability. The present work investigates the idea of upgrading solar heat production with the utilization of excess electricity from renewables for producing industrial process heat. Specifically, the present work investigates the use of efficient evacuated flat plate solar thermal collectors coupled with a thermal storage tank for supplying a reverse air Brayton heat pump for high-temperature production. The analysis is conducted with a developed algorithm in Matlab which takes into consideration the energy balances in all the system components and solves the examined phenomena in dynamic conditions. The analysis is conducted for the location of Komotini, Greece and the results regard the operation of the system for a typical summer week. For the baseline design point with a 1000 m² collecting area and 50 m³ thermal tank volume, the average daily process heat production for the industry is 8.63 MWh, while the average daily coefficient of performance for the heat pump is 1.478. Moreover, the present work includes results regarding the parametric performance of the system for different combinations of collecting area and thermal tank volume.

Keywords: Solar Energy, Heat pump, Reverse Brayton cycle, Waste heat recovery, Industrial process

INTRODUCTION

High-temperature heat upgrade is necessary in various industrial applications for reducing the CO₂ emissions [1]. Renewable energy sources can be properly integrated into heat upgrade units aiming to increase their efficiency and also to make possible heat production in high temperatures. Solar thermal systems are promising choices for leading to sustainable and viable industrial heat upgrade configurations.

THE HTHP SYSTEM

Fig. 1 depicts the studied system that incorporates solar thermal (ST) collectors, coupled with a thermal energy storage (TES) tank that will supply heat into a high-temperature heat pump (HTHP) that operates with a reverse air Brayton cycle.

Fig.1. HTHP cycle configuration including solar thermal system, storage tank and heat pump

The solution is a part of the EU Horizon project, SOLINDARITY which aims to heat upgrade with high efficiency in different areas of the industrial sector. More specifically, one of the demonstration sites of the project is the Komotini Paper Mill, located in Komotini, Greece. For the case of Komotini, a constant air flow rate of 8.23 kg/s is required to be upgraded from 150°C to 195°C in a 24/7 basis.

1. The Reverse Brayton Cycle

The HTHP operates with a reverse Brayton cycle which is presented in Fig.1. The cycle consists of three heat exchangers (HEX) a compressor and a turbine, while the working medium is air. The purpose of the cycle is to increase the temperature of a given medium in HEX-3. For that reason, the heat stored in the TES tank is used in HEX-1 to heat the air in the cycle. The air is heated further in HEX-2 before it enters the compressor which is driven by electricity produced by the PV panels. After the HEX-3 the air enters the turbine to generate power and finally returns to HEX-1.

2. System Modelling

The solar energy will be calculated by taking into account the weather data for the region of Komotini, Greece from PVGIS and the efficiency of the solar collectors [2]. The TES tank is modelled with the mixing zone modelling, taking into account the heat losses to the environment, according to similar studies in the literature [3]. Finally, for the modelling of the HTHP, the energy

equilibriums and isentropic processes have been considered for the HEXs and the compressor and turbine respectively.

3. Results and Discussion

For a total collector area of 1000 m² combined with a 50 m³ TES tank volume, the average daily heat production, in a typical summer week, is 8.63 MWh with a COP of 1.478. Fig.2. illustrates the average daily COP of the HTHP. It is observed that COP is in the range of 1.43-1.49.

Fig.2. Daily average COP of the HTHP

Fig.3. Exergy efficiencies of the ST panels, the HTHP and the system as a whole with respect to time

Fig.3. shows the exergy efficiencies of the ST panels, the HTHP pump and the system with respect to time. It should be noted that when the exergy efficiency of the ST panels is zero the collectors are not operating and the HTHP works with the energy stored in the TES tank. Fig.4. exhibits the influence of the total ST collecting area and the volume of the TES tank on the COP of the HTHP. It is observed that, in a typical summer week, higher COP is obtained when the total

collector area and the ratio of the collecting area to the TES tank volume are increased.

Fig.4. Average COP for different collecting areas and the ratio of the TES tank

CONCLUSIONS

In the present work, a novel heat upgrade system that combines ST collectors with a TES tank arrangement coupled to a reverse air Brayton heat pump is proposed to produce process industrial heat. The daily average COP of the HTHP for a typical summer week in Komotini, Greece is 1.478 while the heat production is 8.63 MWh. Furthermore, the exergy efficiencies have been calculated while a parametric investigation regarding the total collector area and the TES tank volume has been conducted.

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